

ICAENS 2024 PROGRAM

Session 1.1			25 SEPTEMBER 2024 09:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-1	09:00-09:10	Fabrication Of Flexible Thin Film Substrates By The Extraction Of CNCs From Cellulosic Materials	Abdul Basit, Hafeez Anwar	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 2
Y-2	09:10-09:20	Deposition time effect on physical properties of sprayed SnS films	Meriem Messaoudi, Lynda Beddek, Hamza Khemliche, Messaouda Khammar, Ouafia Belgherbi, Samah Boudour	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3
Y-3	09:20-09:30	Behavioral Analysis and Numerical Modeling of Retaining Walls in Deep Excavations	Bencheikh Messaouda, Aidoud Assia, Boukour Salima, Belabed Lazhar	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4
Y-4	09:30-09:40	California Bearing Ratio (CBR) of Engineered Sand Backfill Admixed with Recycled Wastes	Lina ZAIDI, Fatima Zohra BENAMARA, Messaouda BENCHEIKH	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 5
Y-5	09:40-09:50	Experimental and Theoretical Study on the Crystal Structure and Reactivity of a New Organic Compound	Nour Eddine Benharkat, Abdelkader Chouaih, Nourdine Boukabcha	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6
Y-6	09:50-10:00	Coupled Integro-Differential Equations with Impulsive Effects Using the Vector Fixed Point Approach	Abdelhamid Bensalem	Algeria	Submission 8
Y-7	10:00-10:10	The connection between education and wellbeing	Dhurata LAMÇJA, Natasha Poroçani	Albania, Albania	Submission 9
Y-8	10:10-10:20	Gate-Source Overlap Engineering for Improved ON-State Current in Silicon Nanotube TFETs	Djemâa Ben Othmane	Algeria	Submission 11
Y-9	10:20-10:30	Thermal Analysis of Disc Brakes Using COMSOL Multiphysics	Elhadj RAOUACHE, Chetbani YAZID, Razik BENDERRADJI, Fares KHALFALLAH, Aissa LAOUISSI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 12
Y-10	10:30-10:40	EFFECT OF AMOXICILLIN ON ANAEROBIC DIGESTION	Bani Kheiredine, Chaima Bensegueni, Chiraz Bouandel, Rayene Bensegni, Wassim Bendjaballah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 13

Session 1.2			25 SEPTEMBER 2024 09:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-11	09:00-09:10	The Implementation of TRIZ in the Design and Analysis of High-Performance Anti-Roll Bars	Nuraini A. A., Muhammad Syaziq M. S., Azmah Hanim M. A.	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 17
Y-12	09:10-09:20	INVESTIGATION OF STRUCTURAL AND OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF MANGANESE DOPED COBALT FERRITE/gCN COMPOSITES	Areej Fatima, Hafeez Anwar	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 18
Y-13	09:20-09:30	Study of the Performance of a Symmetric solar still	Adel Deliou, Mohamed Chaour, Khmissi Belkaid, Meriem Dehbi, Abdelkader Fidjah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 25
Y-14	09:30-09:40	Optimizing Resin for Cationic Dye Adsorption: Insights from Kinetic and Isotherm Studies	HAMADI Amel, YEDDOU- MEZENNER Nacera, KAIS Hiba, BANSAAADI Zohra	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 26
Y-15	09:40-09:50	Controllability of Mild Solutions for Nonlocal Fractional Evolution Problems with Finite State-Dependent Delay	Chahrazed Boudefla, Selma Baghli- Bendimerad	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 28
Y-16	09:50-10:00	Inference for Seasonal Functional Autoregressive Process	Fatna Bensaber, Amina Benramdane	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 30
Y-17	10:00-10:10	A Mild PC-Asymptotically Almost Automorphic Solutions for Integrodifferential Equations. with Non-Instantaneous Impulsive	Nadia Ikhlef	Algeria	Submission 32
Y-18	10:10-10:20	On behaviors of the energy of solutions for a class of p-Laplacian wave equation	Kamel Yahiaoui, Nacera Helal, Soufiane Mokeddem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 34
Y-19	10:20-10:30	Diet of high-level athletes and its relationship with physical performance - case of football players –	Fethi Derbal, Habib Agboubi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 35
Y-20	10:30-10:40	Tailoring the Growth of ZnO Nanorods Using an Effective SILAR Deposition Technique	Hadjer Barkat, Elhachmi Guettaf Temam, Hachemi Ben Temam, Nour Elhouda Mokrani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 37

Session 1.3			25 SEPTEMBER 2024 10:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-21	10:00-10:10	Statistical Analysis and Numerical Study for the Optimization of Magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) Mixed Convection in Ventilated Cavities Using Nanofluids	Benderradji Razik, Fares Khalfallah, Raouache Elhadj	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 39
Y-22	10:10-10:20	Treatment of raw water loaded with nitrite ions by chemical oxidation with sodium hypochlorite	Baloul Hakim, Amitouche Mourad, Benrachedi Lokmane, Boussalah Nadira, Ali Boudhar Nour El Houda	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 40
Y-23	10:20-10:30	Treatment of raw water loaded with manganese ions (Mn ²⁺) by chemical oxidation with sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl)	Baloul Hakim, Amitouche Mourad, Benrachedi Lokmane, Boudjemaa Safaa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 41
Y-24	10:30-10:40	Treatment of raw water loaded with manganese ions (Mn ²⁺) by chemical oxidation with potassium permanganate (KMnO ₄)	Baloul Hakim, Amitouche Mourad, Benrachedi Lokmane, Bendou Zina, Boualili Lamia, Bendou Zina	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 42
Y-25	10:40-10:50	AI-Powered Design Revolution Through ntopology Software: Application on Continuum Robots	Djeffal Selman	Algeria	Submission 43
Y-26	10:50-11:00	Development of a New Eco-Bio-Sourced Insulating Material for Improving the Hygrothermal Properties of Building Envelopes	Mohammed KSOURI, Abdelmadjid LASLEDJ, Kamilia ABAHRI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 44
Y-27	11:00-11:10	Study of the Workability of Self-Compacting Concrete (SCC) Using Experimental Methods and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)	Salem Merabti, Amar Mezidi, Mourad Serikma	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 45
Y-28	11:10-11:20	EF/VOF numerical study of substrate oxidation's effect on the thermal and dynamic behavior of lamella formation	Tahar Souad, Zirari Mounir, Saidoune Fatmazohra, Ykrelef Hichem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 47
Y-29	11:20-11:30	Activated carbons from macadamia nuts: synthesis and characterization	Souha Harabi, Sami Guiza	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 50
Y-30	11:30-11:40	Seismic Response of Wind Turbines: The Influence of Foundation Length and Soil-Structure Interaction	Nesrine MELLAS, Abdelhak MABROUKI, Kamel HEBBACHE, Mekki MELLAS	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 52

Session 1.4			25 SEPTEMBER 2024 10:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-31	10:00-10:10	Electronic waste and its impact on the environment and human health: Ecological threat and management	Vezire Shaqiri, Milihate Aliu	Kosovo, Kosovo	Submission 55
Y-32	10:10-10:20	Optical and Electronic properties of FeNi ₂ Mn and FeNi ₂ Cr alloys using density function theory	Baira Fayçal, Zidani Sara	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 56
Y-33	10:20-10:30	The cultivation and propagation of caper in Morocco	Naoual Saifi, Jamal Ibibjijen, Ghizlane Echchgadda	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 57
Y-34	10:30-10:40	Design of a chemical / electrochemical reactor used in the recycling of lithium of used Lithium-batteries	Abdelkader Saila	Algeria	Submission 59
Y-35	10:40-10:50	Spin 3/2 Core and Spin 3 Shell of a Cylindrical Ferrimagnetic Nanotube: Hysteresis Behaviors	A. El Abbassi, M. Salama, N. Hachem, E.B. Choubabi	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 60
Y-36	10:50-11:00	First principal study of structural, electronic and magnetic, properties of NdCo ₂	R. Masrour	Morocco	Submission 64
Y-37	11:00-11:10	Study of optical, thermodynamic and thermoelectric properties of rare earth NdFe ₂	R. Masrour	Morocco	Submission 65
Y-38	11:10-11:20	Study of optical, thermodynamic and thermoelectric properties of Pr ₂ Rh ₃ Ge	R. Masrour	Morocco	Submission 66
Y-39	11:20-11:30	Performance Enhancements and Innovative Developments in SG-FD-SOI MOSFETs	Fatima Zohra RAHOU	Algeria	Submission 70
Y-40	11:30-11:40	Solubility diagrams of camphor using β -cyclodextrin	Hayet Ahlem LEZRAG, Sofiane FATMI, Zahra TOUTOU Piotr, P. WIECZOREK, Mohamed SKIBA, Mokrane IGUEROUADA	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Poland, France, Algeria	Submission 72

Session 1.5			25 SEPTEMBER 2024 11:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-41	11:00-11:10	Enhancing PV-Powered Electric Vehicle Charging Stations through Advanced Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) Techniques	TRAIBIZ Omar, OULAD BEN ZAROUALA Rachad	Morocco, Morocco	Submission 73
Y-42	11:11-11:20	Qualitative analytical results of complex order nonlinear fractional differential equations with robust control scheme	Abdelatif Boutiara	Algeria	Submission 74
Y-43	11:20-11:30	Impact and Deposition of Single and Dual Metal Droplets on Solid Substrate	Amel Hadjeri, Mounir Zirari, Mouhamed Kezrane	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 75
Y-44	11:30-11:40	From Polls to AI: Shaping Elections through Public Opinion Technology	Abdelkrim Dekhakhena	Algeria	Submission 78
Y-45	11:40-11:50	Absorption spectra of heterostructure of van der Waals: First principal	Widad LOUAFI, Karim REZOUALI	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 79
Y-46	11:50-12:00	Viability result for Caratheodory non-convex functional differential inclusion in Banach space	Moufida AMIOUR	Algeria	Submission 82
Y-47	12:00-12:10	Elimination the mixture of two dyes (malachite green and Gentian violet) using Barbary fig seeds extract as bio-coagulant	MOKHATI Aya, AISSOUS Bochra, FERROUDJ Nawal, BENALIA Abderrezzaq, DERBAL Kerroum	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 83
Y-48	12:10-12:20	Valorization of the Hydrolate of Salvia officinalis L	Bouhenni Rania Chahinez, Koula Doukani, Hasna Bouhenni, Benslimane Chaima	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 85
Y-49	12:20-12:30	Influence of the Content of Jute/Luffa Reinforcements on the Tensile Behavior of an Epoxy/Jute/Luffa Hybrid Material	Abdelmalek ELHADI, Mohamed Slamani, Mustapha Arslane, Salah Amroune	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 87
Y-50	12:30-12:40	Complexity of interior-point methods for linear optimization problems based on a parametrized kernel function with a double barrier	Bachir Bounibane, Abderrahim Guemmaz	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 88

Session 1.6			25 SEPTEMBER 2024 11:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-51	11:00-11:10	Assessment of antibacterial activity of calcium fluorohydroxyapatite	AGSOUS Maissa, Khireddine Hafit, YALA Sabeha	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 90
Y-52	11:11-11:20	Microbial Pollution Study of Butrinti Lagoon Ecosystem and Shellfish Safety	Elvira Beli, Sonila Çoçoli	Albania, Albania	Submission 91
Y-53	11:20-11:30	MICROBIOLOGICAL SAFETY AND QUALITY OF FOOD OF ANIMAL ORIGINE IN ALBANIA	Elvira Beli, Liljana Lufo	Albania, Albania	Submission 93
Y-54	11:30-11:40	Examination of Fractional Solitary Wave Propagation with Parametric Influences in the Modified Korteweg-de Vries-Kadomtsev-Petviashvili Equation	Riadh Hedli	Algeria	Submission 95
Y-55	11:40-11:50	Synthesis and characterization of low cost adsorbent and their application in water treatment	Akacha Imane, Merzougui Abdelkrim, Bouzid khadidja	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 97
Y-56	11:50-12:00	Crystal Structure, Molecular Docking and Toxicity Assessment of 2-((2, 4-dimethoxybenzylidene) hydrazono) -1, 2-diphenylethanone [DBHDE]	Samia DJABBOUR, Nourdine BOUKABCHA, Abdelkader CHOUIH	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 98
Y-57	12:00-12:10	Remediation of pharmaceutical contaminants by biochar: Machine learning prediction	Akacha Imane, Merzougui Abdelkrim, Bouzid Khadidja	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 99
Y-58	12:10-12:20	Medical Image Processing Using Deep Learning	Fella Berimi	Algeria	Submission 100
Y-59	12:20-12:30	Analysis of Heat Transfer by Mixed Convection in a Ventilated Cavity Filled with Hybrid Nano-Fluid: A Numerical Approach	Fares Khalfallah, Razik Benderradji, Meryem Brahimi, Elhadj Raouache	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 106
Y-60	12:30-12:40	Adaptive control for fractional-integer orders systems synchronization	Fareh Hannachi	Algeria	Submission 107

Session 1.7			25 SEPTEMBER 2024 12:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-61	12:00-12:10	Impact of Dispersants KD1 and DAV7 on the Rheology of Algerian Kaolin Suspensions	Chargui Fouzia	Algeria	Submission 108
Y-62	12:11-12:20	A reaction-diffusion model for Alzheimer's disease	Salim Mesbahi, Samiha Djemai	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 110
Y-63	12:20-12:30	Environmental Education Through Evaluation of Organic Pollutant in the Fierza Lake	Ilijana Osmani, Zeqir Veselaj, Fatlume Berisha, Aurora Nuro, Bledar Myrtaj, Arben Haziri, Aurel Nuro	Kosovo, Kosovo, Kosovo, Albania, Albania, Kosovo, Albania	Submission 112
Y-64	12:30-12:40	Study of the Adsorption Characteristics of Various Aqueous Substances Using a Local Adsorbent	MECHRAOUI Nessrine, DJEDID Mebrouk, BENALIA Mokhtar, BOUDAUD Asma	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 113
Y-65	12:40-12:50	Impact of Traditional Materials on Building Thermal Performance and Energy Efficiency	KERSENNA Soumaya	Algeria	Submission 120
Y-66	12:50-13:00	Incidence of rotavirus infection in suckling pigs in Albania	Kastriot Korro, Anita Koni, Liliana Caro, Mirije Elezi, Besnik Elezi	Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 147
Y-67	13:00-13:10	IS AGE A RISK FACTOR FOR BANANA ALLERGY IN CHILDREN?	Griselda Korçari, Mirela Lika (Çekani), Artan Trebicka	Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 160
Y-68	13:10-13:20	Antimicrobial Resistance in Escherichia coli and Salmonella in a farm to fork approach, in Albania	Tana Kika, Jonida Boci, Sonila Çoçoli, Nikola Puvača, Antonio Camarda	Albania, Albania, Albania, Serbia, Italy	Submission 162
Y-69	13:20-13:30	Modeling the Structural Behavior of FRP-Confined Concrete Composite Columns	Shahir Ahmad Safi, Ali Raza, Raja Tufail Hussain Khan, Muhammad Abbas Ali	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 163
Y-70	13:30-13:40	Review of Mycotoxins Adsorbents on Nephrotic Enteritis Occurrence in Poultry	Tana Shtylla Kika, Sonila Cocoli, Nikola Puvača	Albania, Albania, Serbia	Submission 164

Session 1.8			25 SEPTEMBER 2024 12:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-71	12:00-12:10	Durability and Performance of Geopolymer Concrete: Sorptivity and Acid Attack Resistance	Shahir Ahmad Safi, Khaled Waleed Radman	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 172
Y-72	12:11-12:20	Technology and its Use in Urban Space	Lindita Kiri	Albania	Submission 189
Y-73	12:20-12:30	Game Theory Approaches to Managing Off-Grid PV Systems, Enhancing PV Performance with Incremental Conductance MPPT, Battery Storage, and SHE PWM Inverters to Achieve Minimal THD	Waqar Ali, Rahmat Ali, Shakir Ullah, Mujeeb ur Rahman, Haseeb Ahmed	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 194
Y-74	12:30-12:40	Prediction analysis of the feasibility of an evaporative cooling system under the Tunisian Sahara climate conditions	Karim Choubani, Abdulaziz Alasiri	Tunusia, Saudi Arabia	Submission 202
Y-75	12:40-12:50	Comparative Isotherm and Kinetic Analysis of Acid Violet 7 (AV7) and Methylene Blue (MB) Adsorption onto MOF-5	Danial Moshtaghi Shafti, Irvan Dahlan, Azam Taufik Mohd Din	Malaysia, Malaysia, Malaysia	Submission 212
Y-76	12:50-13:00	The use of technology in the application of organizational reflex in sustainable and environmentally friendly tourism	Palmira Papsiene	Lithuania	Submission 218
Y-77	13:00-13:10	Economic Problems in Laying Hens Production Infested with Red Poultry Mite (<i>Dermanyssus gallinae</i>)	Tana Shtylla Kika, Ivana Brkić, Sonila Cocoli, Dragana Ljubojević Pelić, Miloš Pelić, Sunčica Vještica, Nikola Puvača	Albania, Serbia, Albania, Serbia, Serbia, Serbia, Serbia	Submission 225
Y-78	13:10-13:20	Biosimilars: An overview analysis	Gledjan Caka, Kesi Mahmutllari	Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 237
Y-79	13:20-13:30	Unsteady Flow Simulation Around Rotor Blades of Vertical Axis Wind Turbine	Amar BERKACHE, Said Zergane, Belkhir Noura	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 243
Y-80	13:30-13:40	The Albanian Insurance Market through History, Development and Future Challenges	Arben Reka, Robert Kosova	Albania, Albania	Submission 246

Session 1.9			25 SEPTEMBER 2024 13:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-81	13:00-13:10	The Importance of Identifying HPV in Men: Carriers and Vectors of Transmission	Fjoralda Bakiri, Mirela Lika (Çekani)	Albania, Albania	Submission 222
Y-82	13:11-13:20	Performance Characteristics of Eco-Friendly Self-Compacting Concrete Incorporating Recycled Materials and Synthetic Fibers	Rachid RABEHI, Mohamed RABEHI, Said ZAOUAI, Naas ALLOUT, Yazid CHETBANI, Mohammed OMRANE, Ouassila BAHLOUL, Mohamed AMIEUR	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 284
Y-83	13:20-13:30	Comparative study of different methods for evaluating the resistance of pipelines with external corrosion and their remaining load capacity	SI TAYEB Nor El Houda, SOUCI-CHAFI Zahia, BOUZID Kouider, MECHRI Abdelghani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 129
Y-84	13:30-13:40	Synthesis and characterization of titanium dioxide thin films for photocatalysis application	EL ALIOUI Sadik, RMLI Ahmad, NOUNEH Khalid	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 130
Y-85	13:40-13:50	Features of the Phycobiliprotein C-Phycocyanin: Evidence from Arthrospira platensis (Spirulina)	Saada Zakia, Charef Nassira, Tamer Fatma Zohra, Belaid Bouthayna, Nasri Hichem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 131
Y-86	13:50-14:00	Rotating Hayward AdS black holes	H. LAASSIRI	Morocco	Submission 133
Y-87	14:00-14:10	Rotating Bardeen AdS black holes	H. LAASSIRI	Morocco	Submission 134
Y-88	14:10-14:20	Rotating regular AdS black holes	H. LAASSIRI	Morocco	Submission 135
Y-89	14:20-14:30	AGROLOK's Innovation in High-Protein Soya Feed for EU Protein Security: Task 1 Results	Muhammad Umair Asghar, Qurat Ul Ain Sajid, Mariusz Grzędzicki, Anna Suda, Maciej Zglenicki, Damian Konkol, Martyna Wilk, M. Gumowski, Mariusz Korczyński	Poland, Poland, Poland, Poland, Poland, Poland, Poland, Poland, Poland	Submission 143
Y-90	14:30-14:40	Enhancing Sustainability and Mechanical Performance of 3D Printing Filaments through Palm Fiber Reinforcement	Hocine Heraiz, Salah Amroune, Khalissa Saada, Riyadh Benyettou	China, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 144

Session 1.10			25 SEPTEMBER 2024 13:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-91	13:00-13:10	Recycling of building demolition waste	BEN AMMAR Ben Khadda, LAHMER Seifeddine Mehdi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 145
Y-92	13:11-13:20	The Role of Limestone in Enhancing the Strength and Durability of Virgin Cork Concrete	Samah Hariz, Fouad Ghomari, Brahim Touil	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 146
Y-93	13:20-13:30	On some classes of operators in semi-Hilbertian spaces and Hilbert spaces	Benali Abdelkader	Algeria	Submission 148
Y-94	13:30-13:40	Application of Large Language Models (LLMs) in the Field of Healthcare	Jandoubi Aymen, El Hamdi Ridha and Njah Mohamed	Tunisia, Tunisia, Tunisia	Submission 183
Y-95	13:40-13:50	Structural Response of Transfer Beams: Evaluating the Effect of Staged Construction	Amina Sadouki, Imane Djafar-Henni	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 184
Y-96	13:50-14:00	Study for the presence of Rift Valley Fever virus in livestock in Central Albania: An update	Liljana Lufo, Bejo Bizhga	Albania, Albania	Submission 185
Y-97	14:00-14:10	Serological study for the presence of Adenovirus II in turkeys and pheasants in major districts of Albania	Liljana Lufo, Kastriot Korro	Albania, Albania	Submission 186
Y-98	14:10-14:20	Determination of Water Holding Capacity in Sorghum	Hamidani Lydia, Arioua Khalil, Boutebba Aissa	Algeria, Russia, Algeria	Submission 200
Y-99	14:20-14:30	CONTROL, MANAGEMENT AND CLASSIFICATION OF TRANSGENDER INMATES IN NIGERIAN CORRECTIONAL CENTERS; A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND CASE EXPERIENCE OF SOME TRANSGENDER EX-CONVICTS	Chigozie James Okereke	Nigeria	Submission 282
Y-100	14:30-14:40	Evaluation of the surface water quality of Porto Romano port, based on physical-chemical parameters	Jonida Tahiraj, Sonila Shehu, Esmeralda Halo, Bledar Murtaj, Elda Marku, Aurel Nuro	Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 294

Session 1.11			25 SEPTEMBER 2024 14:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-101	14:00-14:10	Numerical modeling of the propagation of a reflective crack within the asphalt layers of a pavement under traffic	Ayoub M'chich, Khalid Nasri	Morocco, Morocco	Submission 316
Y-102	14:11-14:20	Paradigms of application of digital technologies and innovations during the COVID-19 pandemic	Nebojša Denić, Jelena Stojanović, Kostadinka Stojanović, Boris Siljković, Momir Milić	Serbia, Serbia, Serbia, Serbia, Serbia	Mail Submission 8
Y-103	14:20-14:30	Educational software of modern trends in development and application	Nebojša Denić, Kostadinka Stojanović, Jelena Stojanović, Momir Milić, Dragan Obradović	Serbia, Serbia, Serbia, Serbia, Serbia	Mail Submission 9
Y-104	14:30-14:40	Digital literacy as a key factor in successful education	Nebojša Denić, Momir Milić, Kostadinka Stojanović, Jelena Stojanović, Aleksandar Milić	Serbia, Serbia, Serbia, Serbia, Serbia	Mail Submission 10
Y-105	14:40-14:50	Extraction and characterization of lignocellulosic fibers from a new Algerian wild plant	Yaakoub Fetimi, Abderrezak Bezazi, Gilberto Garcia delPino, Paulo N.B. Reis, Fabrizio Scarpa	Algeria, Algeria, Brazil, Portugal, UK	Submission 219
Y-106	14:50-15:00	Optimizing the Physico-Chemical Properties of Iron Production: Addressing Defects and Enhancing Quality Control at Kurum International	Luan Kola	Albania	Submission 241
Y-107	15:00-15:10	Comparative Analysis of Pipeline Repair Methods: Focus on Composite Systems	Khaled Bachioua, Mohammed Bettayeb, Abdelhakim Maizia, Abderrezak Bezazi, Abdelkader Hocine, Allouti Mustapha, Omar Bouladroua, Paulo N.B. Reis, Fabrizio Scarpa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Portugal, UK	Submission 249
Y-108	15:10-15:20	LUNG CANCER DETECTION USING CONVOLUTION NEURAL NETWORK	Adnan Zeb, Fazal Muhammad, Atta Ullah Jan	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 272
Y-109	15:20-15:30	Early stage Chronic Kidney Disease Prediction using Random Forest Algorithm; A machine learning approach	Aamir Sohail, Fazal Muhammad	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 279
Y-110	15:30-15:40	Improving power quality with a hybrid active power filter based on fuzzy logic controller	SARRA Mustapha, DJAZIA Kamal, BOUDECHICHE Ghania	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 283

Session 1.12			25 SEPTEMBER 2024 14:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-111	14:00-14:10	Solar Active Power Filter Based on Direct Power Control	SARRA Mustapha, DJAZIA Kamal	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 287
Y-112	14:11-14:20	Power Quality improvement of Grid-tied Photovoltaic System using Shunt Active Power Filter	SARRA Mustapha, DJAZIA Kamal, BOUDECHICHE Ghania	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 292
Y-113	14:20-14:30	Advanced DPC Based Shunt Active Power Filter for Power Quality enhancement in Grid Connected PV System	SARRA Mustapha, DJAZIA Kamal, BOUDECHICHE Ghania	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 293
Y-114	14:30-14:40	Steady State Contingency analysis of a multi-bus bar transmission network	Najmul Qamar, Muhammad Bilal, Ajmal Farooq	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 315
Y-115	14:40-14:50	Threatened species of benthic invertebrates along the Himara coast, Albania	Stela Ruci, Anisa Toska, Denada Kasemi, Brunilda Veshaj, Sajmir Beqiraj	Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 332
Y-116	14:50-15:00	Experimental Analysis of The Influence Due to a Backing-Plate on The Monotonic Behaviour of T-Stub	Mohammed Mokhtar FEKIR, Anis ABIDELAH, Hichem Rakib SEBBAGH, Djamel Eddine KERDAL	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 150
Y-117	15:00-15:10	LC-ESI-MS/MS analysis of the hydromethanolic extract of the Algerian endemic <i>Dianthus sylvestris</i> subsp. <i>aristidis</i> (Batt.) Greuter & Burdet	Amina Bouzana, Zohra Chekroud, Imène Becheker, Nora Sakhraoui	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 154
Y-118	15:10-15:20	Building partnerships and resolving state-specific issues in the Indian Himalayan Region (IHR)	Syed Rouhullah Ali, Mahendra Singh Lodhi	India, India	Submission 159
Y-119	15:20-15:30	The Impact of Green Spaces on Mental Health and Social Well-Being in Urban Areas	AFRI Amira, Rahim Ouahab, Kebaili Feriel Khaira, Mellouk Fatma Zohra, Saily Linda, Arif Salah, Triret Tabet	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 165
Y-120	15:30-15:40	Antibacterial efficacy of <i>Thymus vulgaris</i> methanolic extract	Mohamed Khiari, Zine Kechrid	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 177

Session 1.13			25 SEPTEMBER 2024 15:00-17:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-121	15:00-15:10	Raw water quality upstream of the Fergoug dam	Cheikh Bergane	Algeria	Submission 178
Y-122	15:11-15:20	Contribution of theory and experimentation to the investigation of expanding clay stabilization with the use of rubber powder and dune sand	Choungache Belgacem, Ben Saada Abd Elhalim, Bkhiti Melik, Zaitri Rebih	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 193
Y-123	15:20-15:30	Valorization of grape waste as potential antioxidant and enzyme inhibitor agents	Fatima Kamah, Abdelkader Basli, Amraoui Abdelatif	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 197
Y-124	15:30-15:40	Reinforcement of soil by using tire-soil technique	Zohra MELAZ, Lyazid GUECHI	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 204
Y-125	15:40-15:50	Ethyl acetate extract of Atriplex Halimus L. from Tébessa region as a corrosion inhibitor: Gravimetric study	Louiza Boudiba, Khaled Rais, Baya Berka, Sameh Boudiba, Karima Hanini, Azza Baccouche	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 206
Y-126	15:50-16:00	Valorization of dam sediments as an adsorbent of a cationic dye	Mazouri BELHADRI, Nasr-Eddine BOUDJENANE	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 207
Y-127	16:00-16:10	Improving Torque Efficiency in Trajectory Planning for an Articulated Manipulator	Inas SAOUD, Asaad CHAHBOUN	Morocco, Morocco	Submission 208
Y-128	16:10-16:20	Study of thin layers of ZnO using the sol-gel method and its applications in the electronic industry	Mounir Rouabah, Abdelghani Khaldi, Nadir Bouarissa, Khelladi Mohamed Reda	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 211
Y-129	16:20-16:30	Effect of boundary conditions on the free vibration analysis of porous functionally graded sandwich plates	Karima Bousmaha, Sid Ahmed Belalia, Sidi Mohammed Chorfi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 216
Y-130	16:30-16:40	Textile dye removal and treatment using prickly pear seeds	Amel BELAYACHI-HADDAD, Noureddine BENDERDOUCHE, Benaouda BESTANI, Cherif HADDAD	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 217

Session 1.14			25 SEPTEMBER 2024 15:00-17:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-131	15:00-15:10	Validation of Pylori Duotect Rapid Blood Test: An On-Site Detection using Flid and CagA Antibody Compared to Standard Diagnostic Methods	Farzeen Bibi, Haseeb Nisar, Muhammad Akram	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 221
Y-132	15:11-15:20	The stability of thin fluid layer flow on an inclined plane under electromagnetic field	Haddad Zakaria, Mehidi Bouam Nadia, Djema Amar, Mehayech Abdelmalek	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 223
Y-133	15:20-15:30	Linear analysis of a liquid film flowing over a wall using Orr-Sommerfeld equation	Haddad Zakaria, Mehidi Bouam Nadia, Djema Amar, Mehayech Abdelmalek	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 224
Y-134	15:30-15:40	The effect of glass powder on the properties of magnesium potassium phosphate cement	Sadji Amel, Mohamed Redda Boudchicha, Derbali Abir, Iguercha Amina	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 227
Y-135	15:40-15:50	Design and Parametric Optimization of an Organic Rankine Cycle Driven by an Evacuated Flat Plate Collector	Abdelmajid Saoud	Tunisia	Submission 229
Y-136	15:50-16:00	Nanotechnology and Nanomedicine	Abir Derbali, Djallel Bouzid, Amel Sadji	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 232
Y-137	16:00-16:10	Innovative use of Aromatic Plants for Allelopathic Weed Control: A Sustainable solution for African Arid Agriculture	Soltane Sabrine, Benmeddour Tarek	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 233
Y-138	16:10-16:20	Integrating smart technologies in ecotourism opportunities development	Riyan Mohammad Sahahiri	Saudi Arabia	Submission 235
Y-139	16:20-16:30	Parallel vector fields on the 4-dimensional oscillator group	MENAD Bendehiba, DERKAOUI Rafik	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 238
Y-140	16:30-16:40	Recycling of Leather and Eggshell Waste: CaCrO Ceramic Pigment for Sustainable Applications	Hadjar BELKACEMI, Mohamed Amine DJILALI, Hichem TAHRAOUI, Salim BOUDIAF, Rachida BOUALLOUCHE	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 250

Session 1.15			25 SEPTEMBER 2024 16:00-18:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-141	16:00-16:10	Erysiphe sambuci, A New Report of Powdery Mildews Fungi on Molecular Basis from Pakistan	Muhammada Jabeen, Najam-ul-Sehar Afshan, Arooma Saleem	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 252
Y-142	16:10-16:20	Leveraging Mobile Agents for Efficient Load Balancing in Large-Scale Networks	Hamza Khemliche, Meriem Messaoudi, Samah Boudour, Ouafia Belgherbi, Leila Lamiri, Assia Tounsi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 260
Y-143	16:20-16:30	the Klein-Gordon particle confined in a one dimensional box in new type of the extended uncertainty principle	MERAD ASMA	Algeria	Submission 268
Y-144	16:30-16:40	Optimizing Perovskite Properties: Leveraging Machine Learning for Accurate Band Gap Prediction	Touati Soundous	Algeria	Submission 278
Y-145	16:40-16:50	Unveiling the chemical profiling of Algerian spineless Opuntia ficus indica seeds oil	Dib Mouna, Benbott Amel, Malaoui Karima, Kelai Elyes	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 280
Y-146	16:50-17:00	Comprehensive DFT Examination of the Electronic, Structural, and Reactivity Properties of Monometallic Complexes	SARA MERAD, MECHERI SABRI, ZOUCOUN BACHIR	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 281
Y-147	17:00-17:10	Analysis of degradation processes of the TPS – Natural filler composites	Marcell János TÓTH, Annamária POLYÁKNÉ KOVÁCS	Hungary, Hungary	Submission 290
Y-148	17:17-17:20	Impact of supplementary cementitious materials on the performance of concrete and its environmental footprint	TERRAH Hanaa Kawther, KAMECH Zine El Abidine, HOUMADI Youcef	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 291
Y-149	17:20-17:30	First-Principles FP-LMTO Analysis of the Structural, Elastic, and Electronic Properties of CuTe	Ala Boulegane, Abderrahim Hadj Larbi, Abdelmalek Mokeddem, Dahane Kadri, Delloula Lakhdari	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 295
Y-150	17:30-17:40	COMPARATIVE STUDY OF DIFFERENT METHODS FOR EVALUATING THE RESISTANCE OF PIPELINES WITH EXTERNAL CORROSION AND THEIR REMAINING LOAD CAPACITY	MADOUI Ikram, SI TAYEB Nor El Houda, SOUCI-CHAFAI Zahia, BOUZID Kouider, MECHRI Abdelghani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 307

Session 1.16			25 SEPTEMBER 2024 16:00-18:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-151	16:00-16:10	Free vibration analysis of sandwich composite plate based on First-order shear deformation theory using p-element formulation	A BELAIDI, SMN SERDOUN, SA BELALIA	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 13
Y-152	16:10-16:20	The Impact of The Geometric Parameters on The Entry Capacity of Roundabouts in Mosul City, Iraq	Iman H. Al-Slevani, Mohammed Yassen Taha	Iraq, Iraq	Mail Submission 14
Y-153	16:20-16:30	Theory and experimentation contribution to the study of using dune sand and rubber powder to increase clay stability	Choungache Belgacem, Ben Saada Abd Elhalim, Bkhiti Melik, Zaitri Rebih	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 236
Y-154	16:30-16:40	Modeling of the impact and solidification of a ceramic droplet in the plasma spraying process	Mouloud Driouche, Tahar Rezoug	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 317
Y-155	16:40-16:50	Green Technologies for the effective extraction of active phytochemicals: A comparative study	SIMOUD Yasmine Lina, NABET Nacim, GUERBOUB Lynda	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 321
Y-156	16:50-17:00	Effect of Sulfuric Acid Attack on the Durability of Concrete Containing Recycled Asphalt Pavement (RAP) Aggregates	AZIEZ Mohammed Nadjib, BAHAZ Abdesselam, ACHOUR Abderraouf	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 322
Y-157	17:00-17:10	Developing an AI Tool for Situational Context Classification: Enhancing User Experience Through Context-Aware Mobile Computing	Hichem Chaalal	Algeria	Submission 326
Y-158	17:17-17:20	Study of the tolerance to water deficit and thermal stress of rapeseed “Brassica napus (L.)” at the germination stage	Tijania hellal	Algeria	Submission 327
Y-159	17:20-17:30	Mastitis in Dairy Cows in the Tiaret Region, Northwestern Algeria	Abdellah MOHAMED CHERIF, Saadia LAABAS, Mohamed Lehbib, KADI Amel	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 328
Y-160	17:30-17:40	Effect weight of material in the outlet molten pool on heat energy and latent heat of fusion in a piece of Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS) made by a 3D printer fused deposition modeling (FDM)	Samir Gouga, Atef Chibani, Adil Bouhadiche	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 329

Session 1.17			25 SEPTEMBER 2024 17:00-19:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-161	17:00-17:10	Innovative Extraction and Sustainable Valorization of Bioactive Compounds BERKATI Asmaa	GUERBOUB Lynda, SIMOUD Yasmine Lina, BERKATI Asma, TENSAOUT Fatima	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 330
Y-162	17:10-17:20	Asymptotic behavior of a wave equation with a delay in the internal fractional feedback and infinite memory	Ahlem Sidi Yekhlef, Ahmed Hammoudi, Soumia Gaouar	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 331
Y-163	17:20-17:30	Evaluation of Glycerol-Citric Acid-Based NADES for Efficient Green Extraction of Bioactive Compounds	BERKATI Asmaâ, BENHAMICHE Nadir, GUERBOUB Lynda	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 334
Y-164	17:30-17:40	The electronic, elastic and optical properties of KTaO3	Chiraz Soundes Bouaita, Meryem Malla, Badis Bennecher	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 335
Y-165	17:40-17:50	Valorization of agricultural residues	Laali Zineb, Rihab Boushaba, Khatima Kaabeche-Djerafi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 340
Y-166	17:50-18:00	Finite Element Analysis of Functionally Graded Pipe Elbows: Behavior and Damage Under Bending Moments	Rafik Medjahed, Mohamed Mokhtari, Hanane Merzouk, Billel Hamza, Sadek Gouasmi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 344
Y-167	18:00-18:10	Electrical Properties of thin InGaN Cap layer for AlGaIn/GaN HEMTs	Aissa Bellakhdar, Fathi Bendelala, Ali Cheknane	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 346
Y-168	18:10-18:20	EXPLORATION OF THE KEY ELEMENTS OF TRADITIONAL RESIDENTIAL HOUSING FOR CULTURAL HERITAGE IN THE SOUTHEAST, NIGERIA	EZE, Chukwudum Jasper, John Agmada Bawa	Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 320
Y-169	18:20-18:30	Investigation of the Energy Use Pattern in Hotel Buildings in Tropical Savannah Climate: A Case Study of Minna	Zhiri, Gabriel Hassan, Bawa, John Agmada	Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 371
Y-170	18:30-18:40	Assessment of the Fundamentals of Plume Dispersion from Lafarge cement Factory	Oluwatoyin Olanrewaju Ajayi, John Agmada Bawa, Tenigbade Yewande Odu	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 378
Y-171	18:40-18:50	Optimizing 6DOF Drone Path Tracking with a GWO-Enhanced Backstepping Controller in Windy Environment	Bouziane GHOUAL, Yssaad BENYSSAAD, Youssef MEDDAHI, Bouziane MELIANI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 392

Session 2.1			26 SEPTEMBER 2024 09:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-1	09:00-09:10	The Relationship Between Soil and Some Endemic Plant Communities Belonging to The Asteraceae Family Growing Naturally Around Karakuyu Marsh (Afyonkarahisar - Turkey)	Ahmet Serteser	Turkey	Mail Submission 1
T-2	09:10-09:20	Relationship Between Gut Microbiome and Cardiovascular Diseases: Pathophysiology	Mehmet ÖZSAN, Nurcan DÖNMEZ	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 2
T-3	09:20-09:30	Structure and Functions of the Cell Membrane: Physiological and Histological Perspectives	Mehmet ÖZSAN, Hasan Hüseyin DÖNMEZ	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 3
T-4	09:30-09:40	Applying Willmore Function on Evolute-Involute Partner Curves in Euclidean 3-Space	FİLİZ ERTEM KAYA, SÜLEYMAN ŞENYURT	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 4
T-5	09:40-09:50	Derin Öğrenme Tabanlı Android Kötücül Yazılım Tespiti	Anıl Utku	Turkey	Submission 14
T-6	09:50-10:00	GÜMÜŞ NANOPARTİKÜLLERİN BİYOMEDİKAL ALANINDA KULLANIMI	Gökhan NUR, Ali AKBULAT	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 22
T-7	10:00-10:10	Fire – Smoke Classification using Machine Learning Methods	Yunus Erođlu, Selen Yücesoy Kahraman	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 46
T-8	10:10-10:20	An Analysis of Hyperelastic Strips with Spacelike Directrix	Gözde ÖZKAN TÜKEL, Tunahan TURHAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 48
T-9	10:20-10:30	Equilibrium Equations of Hyperelastic Strips with Spacelike Base Curves with Timelike Principle Normal Vector Field	Gözde ÖZKAN TÜKEL, Tunahan TURHAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 49
T-10	10:30-10:40	Başgöz Çayı (Finike) Hidrojeokimyasal Özellikleri	Ayşen DAVRAZ, Fatma AKSEVER	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 54

Session 2.2			26 SEPTEMBER 2024 09:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-11	09:00-09:10	Fiber Laser Peening of Ti6Al4V Alloy Considering the Effects of Laser Power, Scan Speed and Overlap Rate on Surface Morphology and Roughness	Satılmış ÜRGÜN, Sinan FİDAN, Mehmet İskender ÖZSOY, Mustafa Özgür BORA	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 58
T-12	09:10-09:20	Investigation of the Effect of the Granular Filter on Transverse Arching Behavior of Zoned Dams in Numerical Analysis	Sadettin Topçu, Evren Seyrek	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 62
T-13	09:20-09:30	Titanyum katkısının Al-7Si alaşımının sertlik ve dayanım değerlerine etkilerinin incelenmesi	Murat HACIOSMANOĞLU, Ali Paşa HEKİMĞOLU	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 71
T-14	09:30-09:40	Performance Effects of Principal Component Analysis on an LSTM-Based Deep Learning Model	Halit Çetiner	Turkey	Submission 81
T-15	09:40-09:50	Chaotic PSO-based optimal voltage controller design for a SEIG system	Haris Calgan, Metin Demirtas	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 101
T-16	09:50-10:00	Thermomechanical vibration response of nanoplates using nonlocal strain gradient theory	Mustafa Eroğlu, Mehmet Akif Koç, İsmail Esen	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 104
T-17	10:00-10:10	Dynamic Behavior of a Beam on Winkler Foundation under Moving Oscillator	Mehmet Akif Koç, Mustafa Eroğlu, İsmail Esen	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 105
T-18	10:10-10:20	Investigation of Bending and Damage Behavior of Thin-Walled Circular Composites Tubes	Ilyas Bozkurt	Turkey	Submission 114
T-19	10:20-10:30	Effect of Inclination Angle on Bending Behavior in Re-Entrant Structure	Ilyas Bozkurt	Turkey	Submission 115
T-20	10:30-10:40	Investigation of the Flexibility Performance of Square Section Composite Squares Using the Ls Dyna Finite Element Program	Ilyas Bozkurt	Turkey	Submission 116

Session 2.3			26 SEPTEMBER 2024 10:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-21	10:00-10:10	Reasons Why Multisim and PSPICE Circuit Drawing Programs are Preferred	İshak Parlar	Turkey	Submission 117
T-22	10:10-10:20	Değer Akış Haritalama (VSM) Yöntemi Kullanılarak Debriyaj Üretim Sürecinin İyileştirilmesi	İrem Salman, Aytaç Yıldız	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 118
T-23	10:20-10:30	Determination of Three Point Bending Strength of Hexagonal Cross-Section Composite Tubes	Ilyas Bozkurt	Turkey	Submission 119
T-24	10:30-10:40	Eigenvalues of a multi-interval boundary value transmission problems	Oktay Sh. Mukhtarov, Kadriye Aydemir, Merve Yücel	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 121
T-25	10:40-10:50	Multi-interval Sturm-Liouville equations with non-separated boundary conditions	Kadriye Aydemir, Oktay Sh. Mukhtarov, Merve Yücel	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 122
T-26	10:50-11:00	Bulanık QFD Yöntemi ile Tedarik Zinciri Yönetim Sisteminin Özelleştirilmesi	Şeyma Çevikol, Aytaç Yıldız	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 123
T-27	11:00-11:10	5G Haberleşme Sistemleri için Anten Tasarımı Arayüzünün Geliştirilmesi	Ayşe Berçem Kayakökü, Abdulkemir Öztekin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 124
T-28	11:10-11:20	Geri Dönüşüm Polipropilen İçerikli İpliklerin Mukavemet Özelliklerinin Araştırılması	Kaan POLAT, Bestem EŞİ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 127
T-29	11:20-11:30	Design and Implementation of a Lake Surface Cleaning Vehicle	İshak Parlar	Turkey	Submission 137
T-30	11:30-11:40	Investigation of the Effects of CO2 Laser Processing Parameters on Kerf Width and Depth in Basalt Fiber Reinforced Epoxy Composites	Satılmış ÜRGÜN, Sinan FİDAN, Mehmet İskender ÖZSOY, Mustafa Özgür BORA	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 138

Session 2.4			26 SEPTEMBER 2024 10:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-31	10:00-10:10	Enhancing Data Privacy in Energy Management Through AI-Based Techniques: A Survey	Fatma Yaprakdal	Turkey	Submission 140
T-32	10:10-10:20	Geosentetik kullanılarak baraj yeri ve rezervuar alanında zemin iyileştirme çalışmaları: Söğüt 2 Barajı Örneği	Mehmet Özçelik, Melike Hatipoğlu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 149
T-33	10:20-10:30	Tekrarlayıcı İzole Uyku Felcinin Olası Nöroanatomik Temelleri - Literatür Taraması	Fulya Yaprak	Turkey	Submission 151
T-34	10:30-10:40	BRAIN BASED CLASSIFICATION WITH IMAGE PROCESSING AND DEEP ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE METHODS IN MATLAB SOFTWARE ENVIRONMENT	Ali Berkan Ural, Mehmet Can Çalım	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 153
T-35	10:40-10:50	Mermer Tozu Katkılı Kil Zeminin Kıvam Limitlerinin Araştırılması	Onur Saran	Turkey	Submission 155
T-36	10:50-11:00	Kil Zeminin Kompaksiyon ve Basınç Dayanımına Mermer Tozunun Etkisi	Onur Saran	Turkey	Submission 156
T-37	11:00-11:10	Naive Bayes Algoritması ile Öğretmenlerin E-postalara Güven Durumunun Saptanması	Esin AVCI	Turkey	Submission 161
T-38	11:10-11:20	DOĞALTAŞ ÜRETİM FABRİKASINDA KLASİK VE BULANIK İSTATİSTİKSEL ANALİZ YÖNTEMLERİ KULLANILARAK EBATLI FAYANSLARIN KALİTESİNİN DEĞERLENDİRİLMESİ	Merve KARAABAT VAROL	Turkey	Submission 168
T-39	11:20-11:30	Thermodynamic Properties of 2-Propanol and Ethylene Glycol Binary Mixtures from 293.15 K to 323.15 K	Aycan ALTUN KAVAKLI, Osman Nuri ŞARA	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 169
T-40	11:30-11:40	Covid-19 Hastasında Yapay Zeka Destekli Bilgisayarlı Tomografi Sonuçları ile Klinisyen Sonuçlarının Karşılaştırılması	Pınar AYYAT	Turkey	Submission 173

Session 2.5			26 SEPTEMBER 2024 11:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-41	11:00-11:10	İzmir Buca Seyfi Demirsoy Eğitim ve Araştırma Hastanesi'nde Görülen Sıcak Çarpması Vakaları ve Kentsel Isınmasının Azaltılmasında Alınabilecek Önlemler	Pınar AYYAT, Gülşah ŞEHİTOĞLU ALPAĞUT, Nurdan ERDOĞAN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 174
T-42	11:11-11:20	Analysis and Evaluation of Grounding Systems in Electrical Installations: Vocational School Case Study	Bekir Dursun	Turkey	Submission 175
T-43	11:20-11:30	FARKLI TÜR AKIŞKANLAŞTIRICILARIN TAZE ve BUHAR KÜRÜ SONRASI SERTLEŞMİŞ BETON ÖZELLİKLERİNE ETKİSİ	Metin DAVRAZ, Simge YİĞİT	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 179
T-44	11:30-11:40	Evaluating Key Factors in Wind Turbine Efficiency	Ammar Aslan, Selahattin Barış Çelebi	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 180
T-45	11:40-11:50	SiC'ün kademeli sıcaklık aşamaları kullanılarak SPS ile sinterlenmesi	Zuhal Yılmaz	Turkey	Submission 181
T-46	11:50-12:00	Development of a Process for Manufacturing Conductive Yarn with Certain Intermittent Lengths	Ediz ERDEM, Ahmet Hayrettin YUZER	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 187
T-47	12:00-12:10	A Fuzzy AHP Approach to Patent Evaluation System	Onur Fehmi Özdemir, Erdal Aydemir	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 188
T-48	12:10-12:20	Doğal Taş İşleme Tesislerinde Kullanılan Katrakların İncelenmesi	Ali Koray ÖZDOĞAN, Servet DEMİRDAĞ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 190
T-49	12:20-12:30	The impact of stoichiometric variations in B(Pb)SCCO-2223 superconducting material on radiation shielding parameters at varying energy levels	Selami AÇIKEL, Selim KAYA, İbrahim DÜZGÜN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 195
T-50	12:30-12:40	Effect of quinoa seed on endoplasmic reticulum stress gene XBP1 expression in insulin-resistant rat liver	Ayşe Usta, Veysel Yüksek, Semiha DEDE	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 196

Session 2.6			26 SEPTEMBER 2024 11:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-51	11:00-11:10	Optimization of The Gelation Time of Urea Formaldehyde Using Different Hardeners	Süheyla Esin Köksal, Orhan Kelleci	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 199
T-52	11:11-11:20	A Method Proposal for Automatic Chromosome Segmentation in Karyotype Analysis	Hakan Yılmaz, M. Kamil Turan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 201
T-53	11:20-11:30	The Pitfalls of AIC: How Overreliance Can Lead to Misleading Conclusions in Mathematical Modeling	Mahir Demir	Turkey	Submission 205
T-54	11:30-11:40	Bazı Aspir (Carthamus tinctorius L.) Çeşitlerinde Farklı Bitki Sıklığının Ham Yağ ve Protein Verimi Üzerine Etkisi	Muhammet ÖZEN, Özden ÖZTÜRK	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 210
T-55	11:40-11:50	Farklı Bitki Sıklığının Bazı Aspir (Carthamus tinctorius L.) Çeşitlerinde Tohum Verimi ve Verim Ögeleri Üzerine Etkisi	Muhammet ÖZEN, Özden ÖZTÜRK	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 213
T-56	11:50-12:00	RSSI Based Real Time Location Tracking System with Edge Computing	Batuhan SOYLU, Merih PALANDÖKEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 220
T-57	12:00-12:10	Implications from bulk-rock geochemistry of host rock and mafic microgranular enclaves of the Çaltı Pluton	Mustafa Eren Rizeli	Turkey	Submission 226
T-58	12:10-12:20	Improving Forecasting Performance with Random Forest Regression Model in Wind Power Generation	Ammar Aslan, Selahattin Barış Çelebi	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 230
T-59	12:20-12:30	The Rise of Turkey's Mediterranean Ports: Economic Impacts and Regional Comparisons in Cargo Handling	Taha Talip TÜRKİSTANLI, Davut PEHLİVAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 240
T-60	12:30-12:40	Assessing the Impact of Failures on Manufacturing: Textile Factory Case Study	Cihat Cagdas Uydur	Turkey	Submission 244

Session 2.7			26 SEPTEMBER 2024 12:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-61	12:00-12:10	Determination of Chemical Compositions and Antioxidant Activity of <i>Alkanna tinctora</i>	Emine Kılıçkaya Selvi	Turkey	Submission 248
T-62	12:11-12:20	Elektroliz Yöntemi ile Atık Yemek Yağından Biyodizel Üretimi: Sıcaklık Etkileri	M. Raşit ATELGE	Turkey	Submission 393
T-63	12:20-12:30	Functional Foods Based on Seafood	Pınar OĞUZHAN YILDIZ	Turkey	Submission 258
T-64	12:30-12:40	The Impact of Manual vs. CAD/BIM Methods in Early Technical Drawing Courses on Third-Year Architectural Design Studio Success	Erdem Yıldırım	Turkey	Submission 265
T-65	12:40-12:50	Toz metalurjisi ile Üretilmiş B4C/SiC Takviye A356 Kompozit Malzemelerin Aşınma Davranışı	Tansel TUNÇAY, Aslı BAHADIR, Badegül TUNÇAY	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 266
T-66	12:50-13:00	Innovative Designs in Wood Materials for Improving Acoustic Performance	İzham KILINÇ	Turkey	Submission 253
T-67	13:00-13:10	Real-Time Condition Monitoring of Electric Elevators Using Piezo and Speed Sensors with LattePanda Microcontroller	Safa Özdemir, Raif Bayır	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 255
T-68	13:10-13:20	Common Silkworm Diseases in Our Country	Nuray ŞAHİNLER	Turkey	Submission 256
T-69	13:20-13:30	<i>Varroa destructor</i> Parasite Biology and Damage to Colonies	Nuray ŞAHİNLER	Turkey	Submission 257
T-70	13:30-13:40	S Shaped-based Textile Metamaterials Absorber in X Band	Ahmet Hayrettin YUZER, Ediz ERDEM	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 262

Session 2.8			26 SEPTEMBER 2024 12:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-71	12:00-12:10	Yapıların Deprem Performansını Artırmak Amacıyla Kullanılan Malzemeler ve Güçlendirme Teknikleri	Ayça AKBAŞ, Özlem ÇALIŞKAN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 274
T-72	12:11-12:20	Tıbbi Atık Yönetiminde Yapay Sinir Ağları Uygulamaları	Züleyha REÇBER	Turkey	Submission 277
T-73	12:20-12:30	Real-Time Recognition of American Sign Language Using Complex Zernike Moments	Selda Bayrak, Vasif Nabiyev, Celal Atalar	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 276
T-74	12:30-12:40	Ağır Metal İyonlarının Sıvı Membran ile Giderimi ve Yapay Sinir Ağı ile Modellenmesi	Züleyha REÇBER	Turkey	Submission 277
T-75	12:40-12:50	Investigating the Impacts on Urban Road Traffic Congestion: A Case Study of Mogadishu, Somalia	Said Abdirahman Mohamud, Nurten Akgün	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 170
T-76	12:50-13:00	Altın Yüzeylerde Kendiliğinden Biriken Monokatmanların Yer Değişim Kinetiklerinin Eş Zamanlı AKM/QCM ile İncelenmesi	Ümit Çelik	Turkey	Submission 191
T-77	13:00-13:10	Dijitalleşen Yaşam Alanları: Akıllı Teknolojilerin Konut Tasarımlarındaki Rolü	İrem Bekar	Turkey	Submission 270
T-78	13:10-13:20	ETAP Yazılım Programı ile FV Enerji Santrallerinin Elektrik Dağıtım Şebekesine Entegrasyonunun İncelenmesi	Doğan ÇELİK, Yusuf Ali YÜCEL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 285
T-79	13:20-13:30	Analysis of an Emergency Department with Screening DOE and DES Methods	Abdulkadir Atalan	Turkey	Submission 286
T-80	13:30-13:40	Periyodik Bir Forma Maruz Kalan Spiral Kanatçığın Geçici Tepkisi	İbrahim Keleş	Turkey	Submission 298

Session 2.9			26 SEPTEMBER 2024 13:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-81	13:00-13:10	The Iman transform approach to linear ordinary differential equations	Nihal Özdoğan	Turkey	Submission 299
T-82	13:11-13:20	Anti-Aging Potential of Calendula officinalis Oil: Inhibition of Extracellular Matrix-Degrading Enzymes and Sun Protection Factor Evaluation	Rukiye Boran Gülen	Turkey	Submission 300
T-83	13:20-13:30	Yüksekte Çalışma da Mevcut ve Olması Muhtemel Tehlikelerin İncelenmesi/Giderilmesi	İrem GÜLER, Orkun DALYAN, Mehmet PİŞKİN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 302
T-84	13:30-13:40	Evaluation of Technological Innovations and Sustainable Strategies in Reducing the Carbon Footprint of Vehicle Emissions	İdris Cesur, Beytullah Eren	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 306
T-85	13:40-13:50	Elektrokardiyogram Sinyallerin Bulanık Mantık Kullanılarak Sınıflanması	Yücel KOÇYİĞİT	Turkey	Submission 310
T-86	13:50-14:00	Crystallographic and Molecular Interaction Analysis of the Copper-Picolinate Complex	Sevgi Kansız, Necmi Dege	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 323
T-87	14:00-14:10	3,5-dinitrobenzoik Asitle N,N,N',N''-tetrametil-1,2-diaminoetan'ın Yük Transfer Tuzunun Kristal Yapısının İncelenmesi	Sevgi Kansız, Necmi Dege	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 324
T-88	14:10-14:20	Tekirdağ İlinde Faaliyet Gösteren Hazır Yemek Üretim ve Toplu Tüketim Sektöründe Çalışanların Bilgi Düzeylerinin Ölçülmesi	Canan TAŞKIN ARAL, Özgür KARADAŞ KONUK, Emine YILMAZ, İsmail YILMAZ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 336
T-89	14:20-14:30	Aroma Üretimi Yapan Firmalarda HACCP Kriterlerinin İncelenmesi	Burç BÖLÜKBAŞI, Özgür KARADAŞ KONUK, Emine YILMAZ, İsmail YILMAZ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 337
T-90	14:30-14:40	Flow-Induced Oscillations of Elliptical Cylinders: A Numerical Investigation	Aytekin Duranay	Turkey	Submission 109

Session 2.10			26 SEPTEMBER 2024 13:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-91	13:00-13:10	Çocuklarda Voleybolun Psikososyal Gelişim Üzerine Etkileri	Necip ARMAN, Ekrem Levent İLHAN	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 5
T-92	13:11-13:20	Çocuklarda Voleybolun Fiziksel-Fizyolojik Gelişim Üzerine Etkileri	Necip ARMAN, Ekrem Levent İLHAN	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 6
T-93	13:20-13:30	The Role of Biophilic Design in Creating Healthy Communities	Nurgül Arısoy	Turkey	Mail Submission 7
T-94	13:30-13:40	Comparison of the activities of 2-(dimethylamino)ethyl and 2-(diethylamino)ethyl-linked molecules against lung cancer	Koray SAYIN, Burak TÜZÜN	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 11
T-95	13:40-13:50	Comparison of the activities of 2-(Piperidin-1-yl)ethyl and (2-Morpholinoethyl)-linked molecules against liver cancer	Koray SAYIN, Burak TÜZÜN	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 12
T-96	13:50-14:00	Blokszincir Teknolojisi Kriptografik Şifreleme Yöntemlerine Yönelik Yapılan Çalışmaların Bibliyometrik Analizi: WoS Örneği	Adem ÖZDEMİR, Hasan KÜÇÜKOĞLU, Serdar AYDIN, A. Kamil KABAKUŞ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 289
T-97	14:00-14:10	Current Research Trends on Distance Education Studies within Cyber Security Concept: Findings from A Bibliometric Analysis	Hasan Küçüköğlü, Adem Özdemir, Ahmet Kamil Kabakuş, Serdar Aydın	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 296
T-98	14:10-14:20	Enhancing Clay Soil Properties in the Thrace Region with Rice Husk Ash	Cancel Çelik Oral, Erdiñ Keskin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 303
T-99	14:20-14:30	Elmalı, Kaş (Antalya) ve Çavdır (Burdur) İlçeleri Domates Seralarındaki Canavar Otlarının (Phelipanche ramosa/ P. aegyptiaca) Yayınlık ve Yoğunluk Durumları	Havva CAN AKSOY, Yasin Emre KİTİŞ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 309
T-100	14:30-14:40	Sismik Sinyaller Üzerinden Otomatik Deprem Tespitinde Farklı Yönlerdeki Dalgaların Performans Karşılaştırması	Y.E. ERDOĞAN, A. NARİN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 312

Session 2.11			26 SEPTEMBER 2024 14:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-101	14:00-14:10	Modeling Traffic Flow and Time Gaps Using Distribution Fitting and Particle Swarm Optimization	Ekinhan Eriskin	Turkey	Submission 313
T-102	14:11-14:20	Innovation Management Capability Assessment: An application in the Manufacturing Industry	Burcu Felekođlu	Turkey	Submission 318
T-103	14:20-14:30	A New Sensor Electrode for Determination of Dopamine, Serotonin, Epinephrine, and Norepinephrine: Dithiooxamide Modified Pencil Graphite Electrode	Şeyma Korkmaz, İbrahim Ender Mülazımođlu, Ayşen Demir Mülazımođlu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 333
T-104	14:30-14:40	Leaf classification with pre-trained neural networks	Memduh Köse, Reşit Mamur	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 338
T-105	14:40-14:50	Investigation of Electrochemical Behavior of 3-Hydroxytyramine Hydrochloride Modified Pencil Graphite Electrode: Usability in Determination of Paracetamol	Şeyma Korkmaz, Shabnam Aliyeva, Aysel Rustamova, İbrahim Ender Mülazımođlu, Ayşen Demir Mülazımođlu	Turkey, Azerbaijan, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 339
T-106	14:50-15:00	MEKATRONİK SİSTEMLERİN 3B YAZICILARLA ÜRETİMİ ÜZERİNE BİR ARAŞTIRMA	Osman ÜLKİR	Turkey	Submission 348
T-107	15:00-15:10	Performance Analysis of a Novel Geothermal-Solar Assisted Polygeneration System with Helium Cycle and Thermoelectric Generator	Gamze Soy Turk, Onder Kizilkan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 350
T-108	15:10-15:20	Thermodynamic Assessment of a Hybrid Biogas, Kalina, and recompression sCO ₂ Brayton Cycle System for Enhanced Energy Recovery	Gamze Soy Turk, Onder Kizilkan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 351
T-109	15:20-15:30	Çok hücreli özgün bir tüp tasarımının basma yükü altındaki enerji sönmleme performansının deneysel olarak incelenmesi	Erhan Cetin	Turkey	Submission 352
T-110	15:30-15:40	Overview of Fungal Lipases Used in Biodiesel Production	Şeyda YILDIZ ARSLAN, Yağmur ÜNVER	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 353

Session 2.12			26 SEPTEMBER 2024 14:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-111	14:00-14:10	Cloning of Komagataella phaffii protein disulfide isomerase (PDI) gene into pGKB	Şeyda YILDIZ ARSLAN, Yağmur ÜNVER	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 355
T-112	14:11-14:20	Yem Bezelyesi-Arpa Karışımlarına Farklı Katkı Maddeleri İlavesinin Silajların Bazı Kalite Özelliklerine Etkisi	Metin DURU, Asuman ARSLAN DURU, Osman YÜKSEL	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 359
T-113	14:20-14:30	Harmful Gases Emitted from Aircraft Engines, Factors Affecting Gas Emission and Effects on Human Health	Ukbe Üsame UÇAR, Burak TANYERİ, Yusuf Yunus ATABAY	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 362
T-114	14:30-14:40	Green Synthesis and Electrochemical Performance of ZnO Nanoparticles for Supercapacitor Applications	Vedat Emin AYZAZI, Mahir GÜLEN, Hamza DÜNYA, Recep TAŞ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 364
T-115	14:40-14:50	SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF NICKEL OXIDE NANOPARTICLES	Alaa Abdulkarim, Aycan Altun Kavaklı, Osman Nuri Şara	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 368
T-116	14:50-15:00	Microwave-Assisted Biosynthesis of Cobalt Oxide Nanoparticles for Supercapacitor Applications Using Ruscus aculeatus Extract	Abdulrahman Obaid, Recep Taş, Hamza Dünya, Mahir Gülen	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 369
T-117	15:00-15:10	SİYAH HAVUÇ POSASINDAN ÜRETİLEN AKTİF KARBONUN SÜPERKAPASİTÖR OLARAK KULLANIMININ BELİRLENMESİ	Mesut KARTA, Serdar ALTIN, Yunus ÖNAL, Tolga DEPCİ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 29
T-118	15:10-15:20	ARI ZEHRİNİN ANTİBAKTERİYEL ETKİNLİĞİ	Nesibe Özge TOY, Nuray ŞAHİNLER	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 358
T-119	15:20-15:30	Microwave-Assisted Green Synthesis of Cu Nanoparticles Using Ruscus aculeatus Extract for Supercapacitor Electrode Applications	Abdurrazzak Hanan, Hamza Dünya, Recep Taş, Mahir Gülen	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 366
T-120	15:30-15:40	Flexural of 3D printed beams	Yasin Kuddusi Kutucu, Muhammet Muaz Yalçın	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 372

Session 2.13			26 SEPTEMBER 2024 15:00-17:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-121	15:00-15:10	Significance of Artificial Intelligence Applications in Industrial Safety	Munevver Yakut	Turkey	Submission 342
T-122	15:11-15:20	Adsorptive behavior of a novel hydrochar adsorbent derived from hazelnut and pistachio peels	Hasan Saygılı, Gülbahar Akkaya Saygılı	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 356
T-123	15:20-15:30	Comparison of Mechanical Properties of MJF Printed Prototypes and Injection Molded Parts in Polymer Fasteners Used in the Automotive Industry	Orkun Öztürk	Turkey	Submission 360
T-124	15:30-15:40	Design of Micro-Functional Surfaces in Automotive Rivet Fasteners Inspired by Biomimicry for Optimized Mechanical Locking and Ergonomic Insertion Forces	Gökşan ŞAN	Turkey	Submission 361
T-125	15:40-15:50	Lifecycle Evaluation of Live Hinges in Automotive Polymer Fasteners Manufactured via Digital Light Processing (DLP): A Study Through Folding Test Analysis	Gökşan Şan	Turkey	Submission 363
T-126	15:50-16:00	Merkezi ve Dışmerkez Ters V Çaprazların Karşılaştırmalı İncelenmesi	Gülhan İnce	Turkey	Submission 367
T-127	16:00-16:10	Intelligent Attack Detection in IoMT Networks Using Machine Learning Algorithms	Selman HIZAL	Turkey	Submission 380
T-128	16:10-16:20	Waste-to-Energy Potential in Turkey's Poultry Industry: Analyzing Trends and Impacts	M. Raşit ATELGE	Turkey	Submission 386
T-129	16:20-16:30	On the Use and Potential of Insects and Insect Products as Biological Materials	A. Kekillioglu, A. Yılmaz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 389
T-130	16:30-16:40	"Entomology-Toxicology-Forensic Sciences: "Forensic Entomototoxicology"	A. Kekillioglu, A. Yılmaz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 390
T-131	16:40-16:50	Electricity Generation from Biogas Plants in Türkiye: Current Situation and Future Prospects	Yiğit Gaspak, Ahmet Çifci	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 354

